

Bachelor Thesis

Breeding for Resistance: Evaluating Common Bunt Resistance in Winter Wheat Genotypes for Organic Agriculture

submitted by

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Affidavit

I solemnly declare under oath that I have written this Bachelor Thesis independently and have used no sources or aids other than those specified. All ideas that have been adopted verbatim or in essential content from unpublished texts, published literature, or generated using artificial intelligence are properly marked, cited, and provided with exact source references. Contributions from colleagues have been explicitly acknowledged in the authorship statement of the published works.

This work has neither wholly nor partially been submitted in the same or a similar form to any educational institution as a requirement for obtaining an academic degree. It fully complies with the guidelines of scientific integrity and the principles of good scientific practice.

Place, Date

Signature Fabian Wolf

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1. Introduction

In the last decades concerns about environmental degradation and food safety have driven the interest in more sustainable cultivation methods in the agricultural sector (FiBL & IFOAM – Organics International, 2022, p. 19). Since it has become a major goal for many countries to avoid synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, the interest in organic farming as an alternative to conventional agriculture has grown. With upcoming new challenges like climate change, resource depletion and pesticide resistance, organic farming may offer viable alternatives for a more environmentally friendly food production. However, the success of organic farming depends heavily on managing crop diseases effectively, particularly in cereal production, a major pillar of global food security (Barbercheck et al., 2011). Winter wheat is one of the most widely grown crops worldwide. Unfortunately it is vulnerable to a variety of fungal diseases, for example common bunt, a soil-borne pathogen that can cause significant yield losses and reduce grain quality (NÖ Landwirtschaftskammer & AGES, 2011). Since the chemical seed treatments that are commonly used in conventional agriculture, are not permitted in organic agriculture, common bunt poses a serious threat. This circumstance sparked a new interest in developing resistant wheat varieties, as an alternative disease management strategy tailored to organic farming conditions. Even though great advances in organic disease management as well as plant breeding have been made over the last decades, common bunt remains a persistent challenge (Matanguihan et al., 2011).

After the 1950s the implementation of highly effective chemical seed treatments caused a decline in efforts to breed resistant wheat varieties (Hoffmann, 1982). Today some plant pathogens, such as common bunt have a resurgence. This seems to be mainly caused by the growing organic agriculture branch. As organic farming systems grow in popularity, the need for research within that area increases as well. Organic Agriculture faces specific challenges in terms of managing diseases because it depends on using natural inputs only. Growing resistant varieties as a part of disease management is fundamental in organic farming. Breeding these varieties, designed for organic agriculture, is yet a complex task. In part because the role that genetics play in disease resistance, especially in relation to common bunt, is still largely unknown (Matanguihan, Murphy & Jones, 2011).

The goal of this thesis is to contribute to the development of new winter wheat varieties with enhanced resistance to common bunt. It specifically explores the role of genetic resistance in

reducing crop losses. Through analyzing experimental data, this study aims to identify genotypes are especially well suited for organic winter wheat production by ensuring more stable yields and higher grain quality.

2. Literature

2.1 The Significance of Wheat and Its Role in Global Agriculture

Wheat is one of the most widely produced, consumed and traded cereal crops in the world, making it a real staple in global food systems. In Europe, Asia, North America and parts of Africa it serves as a main food source for billions of people. Therefore wheat is grown on about 220 million hectares, making it the second largest crop after corn in terms of land use. Billions of people rely on it as a major source for calories and nutrients as well as farmers, for which it is a vital source of income (Erenstein et al., 2022). Wheat is a main ingredient in many cuisines and is prepared in various forms for example as Pasta, bread or pastries. Furthermore, wheat is commonly used as animal feed as well as for biofuels, and various industrial processes, which emphasizes its economic significance worldwide. Wheat can thrive in various climates, from temperate zones to semi-arid areas. The worlds largest producers China, India, Russia, the United States, and the European Union contribute most of the global output, which came to about 700 million metric tons in 2020 (FAO, 2020, p. 11). While some areas mainly grow wheat for local consumption, others play an important role in exporting it to countries in the Middle East, North Africa, and Southeast Asia (Erenstein et al., 2022). The Way in which wheat is consumed varies between regions. Wealthier countries mostly process wheat into pasta or bread while developing regions prefer flatbread, noodles or porridge (Erenstein et al., 2022). In guaranteeing global food security as well as fighting hunger and malnutrition wheat plays a crucial role, as it provides carbohydrates, dietary fiber and nutrients like B-vitamins, zinc and iron (Shewry, 2009).

Apart from being an essential part of food security, wheat production is also an economical factor, as millions of farmers, especially smallholders in developing regions, rely on wheat production as their main source of income (Lowder, Sánchez, & Bertini, 2021). Moreover, it is a fundamental commodity to industries like milling, baking, and biofuel production, creating jobs, economic growth and adding value in both rural and urban places. Wheat is also ranking as one of the most

traded agricultural products, making it an significant factor in international trade. Any disturbance in wheat production such as pests, geopolitical issues or extreme weather as well as supply chain issues can cause significant impact on the economies of countries and may affect both importing and exporting countries alike (Fair, Bauch, & Anand, 2017).

A great challenge farmers face today, is to make wheat production more sustainable, while global demand constantly increases due to population growth and changing dietary preferences. In addition to that rising temperatures, changing rainfall patterns, and extreme weather events, are further impacting wheat yields and threaten farming in some traditional regions (Shiferaw, Smale, Braun, Duveiller, Reynolds, & Muricho, 2013). Wheat is highly susceptible to various pests and diseases, which can significantly cut down on yields as well as quality. Fungal diseases like wheat rusts, powdery mildew, and common bunt are especially concerning. Therefore effective disease management is crucial to keep production levels up and help ensure the sustainability of wheat farming (Duveiller, Singh, & Nicol, 2007).

The rising demand and the necessity to solve environmental problems through a more sustainable production has increased the interest for organic farming methods, that boost soil health, enhance biodiversity, and decrease dependency on synthetic inputs (Gomiero, Pimentel, & Paoletti, 2011). Nevertheless, fighting fungal diseases, for example common bunt, remains a great challenge in organic systems, mainly since the most effective tool which is chemical seed treatment, is not permitted (Hoffmann, 1982)

As a result of that, developing disease-resistant wheat varieties is becoming increasingly important. Strongly resistant cultivars are an effective alternative to chemical crop protection. They are not only more sustainable by decreasing environmental pollution, they additionally reduce management costs as farmers save on costs for chemical seed treatments and fuel. Apart from the genetic resistance cultivars have, crop rotation, biological control and integrated pest management significantly influence the impact of diseases. Therefore combining these different methods of crop protection is the most effective way to reduce yield losses (Spieß et al., 2015). Plant breeding plays an important role to ensure the sustainability and resilience of global wheat production. Breeding new varieties, that are better able to handle environmental stresses, like drought or heavy rainfall, can help to take on challenges of the future, that go along with climate change (International Centre for Agricultural Research in Dry Areas [ICARDA], Tadesse, Halila, Jamal, Hanafi, Assefa, Oweis, & Baum, 2017). Moreover, breeding for resistance to diseases like common bunt can contribute to

cut down the need for chemical solutions and offers a practical alternative for organic farming systems. Resistant varieties not only ensure yields and grain quality but also help to increase biodiversity within agricultural ecosystems. Furthermore farmers become less reliant on buying products like fungicides, which supports their self-sustainability. The genetic diversity that is achieved through breeding may help to support crop adaptability to changing growing conditions in the future. In organic farming, where conventional chemical pest control is not allowed, breeding for resistance is one of the most effective strategies for addressing ongoing challenges like fungal diseases, while supporting environmentally friendly practices.

2.2 The Threat of Common Bunt

Common bunt is definitely one of the greatest threats in organic wheat production. This fungal disease, is both soil- and seed-borne and infects the plant right at germination, replacing healthy kernels with spore filled bunt balls that spread a strong, unpleasant, fishy smell. Not only does common bunt lead to direct losses in yield, but it also decreases grain quality, making heavily affected crops practically unsellable. While conventional farming has an effective way to control common bunt with chemical seed treatments, these options are not allowed for organic farmers. Therefore controlling common bunt is still a tough challenge for those growing organic wheat. This has sparked the interest in finding alternative disease management strategies, like developing resistant varieties and exploring non-chemical control methods (Matanguihan, Murphy, & Jones, 2011). The recent resurgence of common bunt in organic farming emphasizes the urgent need for sustainable solutions to safeguard wheat crops and maintain steady yields.

Common bunt, caused by the fungi *Tilletia caries* and *Tilletia laevis*, follows a distinctive life cycle starting with teliospores being present in the soil or on seed surfaces. The spores can survive for several years in this state, enabling the disease to stick around even through tough conditions. When susceptible wheat seeds germinate, those teliospores germinate right along with them, creating infectious sporidia, which infect the coleoptile, or seedling shoot, and start to grow throughout the plant, reaching the developing wheat spikes. As the wheat matures, spore-filled bunt balls develop, replacing the healthy grains. Each of these bunt balls holds millions of teliospores, which are distributed during the harvest or handling, spilling contamination onto the soil, equipment, and neighboring crops. The cycle repeats when contaminated seeds are planted or teliospores from the soil wreak havoc on subsequent crops. The infection is almost undetectable during the vegetative growth stages. Distinct Symptoms show up later when the heads of infected plants fail to produce healthy kernels and instead form bunt balls, giving off a characteristic and unpleasant odor from

trimethylamine. When wheat fields are heavily infected with this disease, the consequences are serious reductions in yield and grain quality, which directly result in economic losses, since the harvest is almost unsellable (Börner, Schlüter, & Aumann, 2009, p. 130; Hoffmann, 1982).

Wheat is essential for global food security, as well as economic and social stability across the World. It is one of the most versatile grains, supporting billions of people and providing livelihoods for countless farmers and industry workers. Nevertheless, wheat production is under increasing threat from diseases. Applying sustainable farming practices, along with innovative strategies like breeding for disease resistance, could contribute to secure the future of wheat production. The growing interest environmental sustainability and organic farming emphasizes the need for ongoing research and development of resistant wheat varieties, especially when it comes to battling challenges like common bunt.

Materials and Methods

3.1 Plant Material

In Order to assess the resistance to common bunt in various winter wheat genotypes, several field experiments, in two locations were conducted over several years. In total, 40 genotypes were tested in a field trial in Prague. In another field trial in Tulln, 66 were tested in 2021 and 82 in 2022. The winter wheat varieties that were tested included both well established winter wheat varieties suitable for organic farming, as well as crosses that were specifically selected for their resistance potential. They were chosen due to their agronomic performance in previous resistance screenings and their suitability to organic farming systems. Therby this study aims to explore the genetic diversity of resistance traits and determine potential candidates for future breeding efforts.

3.2 Inoculation and Field Trial setup

The seed materials were artificially inoculated withTeliospores, following the protocol established by Goates (1996). To help the spores adhere to the seeds a methylcellulose solution was applied. This method ensured a final concentration of 0.75 g of spores for every 100 g of seeds.

Figure 1: Inoculation of seeds with teliospores (Pfatrishch 2021) *Figure 2: Inoculated seeds (Pfatrishch 2021)*

The field trials assessing common bunt resistance were executed at the experimental fields of the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences in Vienna (BOKU), specifically at the Department of Crop Sciences at the Institute of Plant Breeding, located in Tulln, Austria (48° 20' N, 16° 3' E). Each tested genotype was grown in a plot measuring 0.5 m², consisting of two rows each 1.5 m long, spaced 17 cm apart, each row containing about 70 plants. The inoculated seeds were sown in November 2020 and 2021, 6 g of seeds treated with common bunt spores per plot.

In July, just before reaching full maturity, the experimental plots were assessed for any signs of infection (Figure 3). For each genotype, 50 individual spikes from each row, totaling 100 spikes per plot were examined. Each spike was cut at a 45° angle three times to visually investigate for black bunt balls filled with spores (Figure 4). A spike was registered as infected if even one diseased floret was detected, and the number of infected spikes for each variety or breeding line was documented.

Figure 3: Overview of the experimental plots (Pfatrish, 2021)

Figure 4: assessment of an infected wheat ear (Pfatrish, 2021)

Figure 5: Experimental setup for a detailed analysis of infected wheat ears (Pfatrish, 2021)

Figure 6: Separation into healthy grains (top) and bunt balls (bottom). (Pfatrish, 2021)

Once the crops reached full maturity, an additional 50 ears of each genotype were randomly selected for further analysis (Figure 5). Each ear was weighed before the healthy grains and bunt balls were carefully separated from the husks, awns, and rachis (Figure 6). The number and weight of the healthy grains and bunt balls was documented. Furthermore, whether the ears we collected were awned or awnless, was noted.

3.3 Comparison of Infection Across Years and Locations

For this analysis, the experiments conducted in Tulln during 2021 and 2022, were compared. Since not the exact same genotypes were tested in both experiments, only the varieties and breeding lines that were grown in both years were compared. The data regarding the experiments for 2021 and 2022 is listed in the Appendix. For the varieties and breeding lines tested in both years, the mean was calculated. In this comparison, the percentage of bunt balls weight relative to the total ear weight (CBWT) is compared to examine if any differences are shown. As shown in Figure 7, the weight percentage correlates with the rate of infected ears. For the varieties grown in the same experiment twice, the mean was calculated as well. Furthermore, the percentage of infected ears (CB), from the experiments in Tulln and Prague was compared, to determine whether the growing location had an influence on the infection rates.

A similar experiment to the one in Tulln was also conducted in Prague. Since the varieties and breeding lines used in both locations were not fully identical, only those tested in both experiments were compared. The varieties and breeding lines used in the Prague field experiment are listed in the Appendix.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

In order to analyse the relationship between ear infection rates (CB.150) and the ratio of buntballs to ear weight (CBWT) in the field experiment, a scatterplot was created. The scatterplot provides a visual illustration of the relationship of the two variables, with each point on the plot representing a sample from the experiment. The x-axis represents the CBWT while the y-axis shows the CB.150. Another scatterplot was generated to inquire the relationship between the percentage of infected seeds (CBS.50, displayed on the x-axis), and the percentage of buntball weight per ear (CBWT, shown on the y-axis) from the same experiment (Figure 8). Additionally, to show the relationship between ear infection rates (CB.150) and the infected seed ratio (CBS.50), a scatterplot was created. The x-axis represents the CB.150 while the y-axis displays the CBS.50. The overall pattern of points on the scatterplot, can provide a brief overview of how these variables might be connected

and whether they might be positively correlated, negatively correlated, or not correlated at all. This Analysis demonstrates how ear infection rates relate to buntball weight and the percentage of infected seeds, as well as on any trends or outliers in the data. The results reveal how common bunt affects crop yields and how different genotypes are resistant to it under changing conditions. Finally, a scatterplot matrix that shows the relationships between ear infection rate (CB.150), proportion of buntballs to ear weight (CBWT), percentage of seeds infected (CBS.50), and the infected seed ratio (CBS.50) was created to show the connections among all these variables at once. The scatterplot matrix allows for the simultaneous comparison of all variables, providing an overview of the data and identifying patterns and outliers in the data.

4. Results

4.1 Association between Ear Infection Rates and severity of infection in the Field Experiment in Tulln 2022

The data from this analysis demonstrate a strong relationship between percentage of infected ears with buntballs and weight of buntballs as a percentage of total ear weight. In Samples that showed low levels of infection (less than 40%) buntballs accounted for less than 10% of the total ear weight. Increased levels of infection were associated with increased percentage of weight of buntballs in the ear. As the infection rate increased, the proportion of weight of buntballs to weight of ear increased disproportionately (Figure 7). Furthermore the data shows that with higher infection rates, the majority of genotypes sampled in this study exhibited partial resistance, as evidenced by the ability to produce a significant amount of kernel mass in comparison to mass of bunballs. Additionally the scatterplot shows that the genotypes that produced less mass of buntballs, had lower rates of ears infected at all.

Figure 8: Relationship between the seed infection rate (CBS.50) and the percentage of buntball weight per ear (CBWT)

Figure 8 suggests a link between percentage of seeds infected (CBS.50) and proportion of buntballs to ear weight (CBWT). With increased percentage of seeds infected (CBS.50) there is an increase in the CBWT. This supports the assumption that the partial resistance present in certain genotypes may reduce the severity of an infection by reducing the percentage of kernels infected with common bunt per ear, not just decreasing the number of ears infected (CB.150) with common bunt.

Figure 9 shows the relationship between the percentage of infected ears (CB.150) and the percentage of seeds infected (CBS.50) in the field experiment. These results show that with increase in the percentage of infected ears, the percentage of infected seeds also increases, suggesting a strong correlation between the two variables. This observation indicates that genotypes which exhibit partial resistance not only lower the number of kernels forming buntballs per ear, but also prevent ears from getting infected in the at all.

Figure 9: Relationship between ear infection rates (CB.150) and infected seed ratio (CBS.50)

Figure 10 scatterplot matrix provides an overview of the relationships between variables ear infection rate (CB.150), proportion of buntball weight to ear weight (CBWT), percentage of seeds infected (CBS.50). The matrix provides a visual representation of the relationship between all variables, where each plot point on the plots represents one sample in the test. From the scatterplot matrix, it can be observed that there is a relationship between the ratio of infected ears (CB.150), percentage of buntball weight per ear (CBWT), and percentage of infected seeds (CBS.50). Partial resistance to common bunt is exhibited by the capacity to avoid an infection of the ear altogether as well as being capable of decreasing the percentage of kernels that form buntballs. Furthermore, the genotypes vary in regards to the kind of resistance they show. Most of the genotypes in the field test could more efficiently hinder the formation of kernels to buntballs, as seen in the ratio of infected seeds (CBS.50), than hinder an infection of the ear (CB.150) in general.

Figure 10: scatterplot matrix which illustrates the comparison of three variables: Genotype (GEN), infected seed percentage (CBS.50), infection rate (CB.150), and percentage of buntball weight per ear (CBWT) in the field experiment in Tulln 2022.

4.2 Comparison of Ear Infection Rates in Field Experiments in Tulln and Prague

To test the potential difference in common bunt infection rates (CB.) between the two locations, Tulln and Prague, a replicated field experiment was conducted in both places. Statistical comparison of the infection rates of the two places was done using both boxplots and a Welch two-sample t-test, in order to determine whether there had been any actual differences in infection levels in the two regions and to determine how conditions in the environment could have influenced the development and spread of common bunt.

Figure 11: Boxplot illustrating the distribution of the infection rate (CB) of the ears, with the location on the x-axis and the infection rate on the y-axis.

The results indicate that there is a wide variation in the incidence of ear infections between the field experiments conducted in Tulln and Prague. The average number of infected ears was compared between the two locations using a Welch's two-sample t-test. A p-value of 0.0003 indicated that the null hypothesis of equality of means can be rejected. The average number of infected ears in Tulln was 12.4 and in Prague 1.67. Furthermore, Levene's test was used to verify testability of

homogeneity of variance between the two locations and a $\text{Pr}(>F)$ of 0.0005 showing rejection of the null hypothesis that variances are equal. These results suggest that the same genotype of *Tilletia* caries tested on the same genotypes of winter wheat in these experiments resulted in infection rates that were significantly higher and more heterogeneous at Tulln compared to Prague. The reasons why these differences occurred are still not known. Therefore further studies are needed to determine the factors that caused the variations in the infection rates between sites. A boxplot was employed to show the distributional differences between the two sites that were investigated. The boxplot is a graphical representation of the five-number summary of a data set, consisting of the minimum value, first quartile, median, third quartile, and maximum value. The box of the boxplot indicates the interquartile range, the range of middle 50% of the data, while the whiskers indicate the minimum and maximum value of the dataset. The use of this statistical measure allowed the depiction of the variability between the data of the two sites, with a visual description of the distributional differences.

4.3 Comparative Analysis of Buntball to Ear Weight Ratios in Tulln Field Experiments: 2021 vs 2022

A boxplot and a Welch's two-sample t-test were employed to compare the infection rates (CB.) of common bunt at the two locations, Tulln and Prague, to identify whether significant differences existed in the susceptibility of the genotypes to infection under different environmental conditions. Experiments were conducted at Tulln in 2021 and 2022 to see if there were any temporal differences in the susceptibility of genotypes to common bunt infection. This analysis provides insight of how environmental conditions can affect the susceptibility of genotypes to common bunt infection and how breeding can be adjusted for different conditions, to raise more resistant crops. The result of the present study presents a significant difference in the ratio of weight that the buntballs make up of the entire ear weight (CBWT) between the field trials conducted at Tulln in 2022 and 2021. The two trials were compared through a Welch's two-sample t-test, whose p-value as calculated was 0, which indicates that the null hypothesis that there is no difference in the means can be rejected. The mean CBWT for 2021 was 13.20, while that of 2022 was 28.03. Furthermore, a Levene's test was applied to determine if there is homogeneity of variances between the two years, and a $\text{Pr}(>F)$ of 0.0006 indicated that the null hypothesis of equal variances can be rejected. These results show that there was a significantly larger ratio of buntballs to ear weight in the 2022 field experiment compared to 2021. The explanations for why this difference in CBWT between the two

years exists must be examined further. It is possible that the environmental conditions, management practices, or other variables were not identical between the two years and they might have a direct influence on the CBWT. A boxplot was generated to show the variation between the data (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Boxplot which illustrates the distribution of the percentage of weight that the buntballs make up of the total ear weight (CBWT) with the year the field experiment was done on the x-axis and the CBWT on the y-axis.

5. Discussion

The association between infection rate (CB.150) and buntball weight per ear as a proportion (CBWT.) (Figure 1) can be explained by the fact that buntballs are much lighter than wheat kernels. Buntballs are quite light compared to wheat kernels, so even a large number of buntballs barely has any effect on the weight of the whole ear. It is to be noted that, however low the percentage of buntball weight to ear weight (CBWT) is, the grain quality is still significantly affected by this factor. Based on industry standards, a maximum of 5 infected plants per 150m² and 20 spores per 16 kernel are permitted for the production of Z-seed and 3 diseased plants out of 150m² for seed production (Wilbois et al. 2007; LFL 2023). Additionally, due to its toxicity and unpleasant smell, grain with a contamination level of 0.1% or higher is not suitable for human consumption and can only be used for animal consumption (Gaudet and Menzies 2012). Furthermore, if buntballs have more than 1% of the weight, the grain cannot be used as animal feed but may be used for methane production or incineration (NÖ Landes-Landwirtschaftskammer & AGES, 2011; LFL 2023). Grain washing is a costly procedure and only feasible for high-grade organic wheat (NÖ Landes-Landwirtschaftskammer & AGES, 2011). Even a fairly small Bunt-Weight-Total can therefore result in severe economic losses. It is also worthwhile to consider the number of spores released during harvesting, as teliospores last for six years in the soil and infect the following crops (Voit et al. 2012). Therefore, breeding for resistance against common bunt should attempt to achieve a percentage of buntball weight to ear weight (CBWT) as low as possible. The percentage of infected seeds (CBS.50) is a critical measurement in assessing the impact of common bunt infection on yield. This is because when a kernel is infected with common bunt, it is fully replaced by a buntball, resulting in a simple loss of yield that can be approximated by the CBS.50. (Gaudet and Menzies 2012). Therefore breeding efforts should aim for a reduction in CBS.50 with the intention of preventing yield loss.

As can be observed in Figure 4, various genotypes show varying degrees of resistance with regard to the overall rate of infection of the ear, and the proportion of buntballs produced. From the interaction between factors CB.150, CBWT, and CBS.50, it is evident that all three of them must be considered in breeding for maximum resistance. The ultimate goal of breeding against common bunt should be to reach full resistance, resulting in absence of infection in the ear. The results of the experiments conducted at Tulln and Prague in 2022 and the comparison of the experiments conducted at Tulln in 2021 and 2022 demonstrate clear differences in the degree of resistance to

common bunt in the tested genotypes of winter wheat . Since the method of inoculation was the same in all experiments, the variation in mean and variance of the infection levels, can be attributed to either different management practices or environmental factors such as soil temperature and water content, which have been reported to impact the infection rate of common bunt (Spieß et al. 2015; Goates 1996). In Tulln the soil temperatures and the amount of rainfall were significantly higher in spring of the year 2022 than in 2021 (BOKU 2023) The warmer and moister weather may caused the higher infection rates, as abiotic factors such as temperature and moisture play a crucial role in common bunt infection. The germination of teliospores and subsequent infection of wheat seedlings are both heavily reliant on such conditions and can have a large influence on disease severity.

Teliospore germination of common bunt in the soil is strongly temperature dependent. The optimum temperature range for germination is between 5°C and 15°C. Temperatures of less than 5°C, as well as temperatures above 20°C have been reported to significantly repress germination (Goates, 1996). A factor that results in common bunt being more prevalent in regions with cooler fall and winter (Gaudet & Menzies, 2012). Presence of water is another relevant factor determining infection rates. Teliospore germination and infection penetration of the seedling coleoptile by the fungal hyphae relies on high soil water content. If the soil is maintained too dry during early growth stages, infection levels are much lower, as the fungus relies on water to induce spore germination and motility towards the host plant (Hoffmann & Waldher, 1981). High rainfall may also reduce infection levels by washing away spores from the area of the seed before the chance to infect the emergent wheat seedlings. Apart from regulating the growth of the fungus, the weather conditions also affect the host plants susceptibility to common bunt infection. Cold and wet weather at the time of seedling germination slows the growth of the plant and extends the time window in which the plant is susceptible to infection. Slower growing seedlings are more vulnerable since common bunt infects primarily the coleoptile before the first true leaves emerge, while faster growing plants can avoid infection by growing faster than the fungus (Matanguihan et al., 2011). By understanding how temperature and humidity affect the infection of plants with common bunt, the differences in infection rates that occurred in the experiments can be interpreted. Lower infection rates in Tulln during 2021 compared to 2022 for example, might be attributed to less humid spring weather, which might have limited germination of teliospores and secondary infection. These findings emphasize the importance of breeding under different environments in order to ensure that resistance is present even when conditions are favorable for the pathogen. The best way to achieve this, is to select genotypes with low variability of resistance. Latest research has identified a few genotypes with

infection rates below 0.01% that can be termed as fully resistant (Spieß et al. 2015; Ritzer et al. 2021; Dumalasova and Grausgruber 2021).

The results of the field experiments conducted in Tulln (2021, 2022) and Prague (2022) showed, that the resistance to common bunt varied greatly among the tested genotypes. While some genotypes were consistently resistant or susceptible across sites and years, others displayed great variability. Some genotypes in particular had much lower infection rates than average, in all three field tests. The Genotypes 516_EX01.6K, 521_EX08.1G, 522_EX09.4G, 559_EX06.14, G559_EX06.4, 702-1102C, BONNEVILLE, UI SRG, BLIZZARD and ARISTARO were highly resistant with very low infection levels, despite being tested under conditions that were highly favorable for the development of common bunt. This suggests that these genotypes might have genetic resistance mechanisms that enable them to suppress spore germination or infection in general. Conversely, other genotypes showed increased susceptibility higher than average with infection levels above the overall mean. Particularly, SEC-313-10 1a_BLICKFANG, SEC-290-08-1a_RUEBEZAHN, SEC-261-05, 522_EX09.N0543K, 522_EX09.N0543G, 521_EX08.3K and URSITA demonstrated much higher buntball production and ear infection levels in all three experiments than anticipated. This is likely caused by a lack of genetic resistance, since even less favorable environmental conditions for common bunt, did not assist the plant in reducing infection rates. The genotypes TILLSTOP, TILLIKO, TILLEXUS, SPONTAN, GRAZIARO, GENIUS, BUTARO, 518_EX03.N0533B.K, 517_EX02.N0532A.G, and 516_EX01.N0547G showed high infection rates in both field experiments at Tulln (2021 and 2022), yet almost no infection in Prague. This difference suggests that these plants have genetic resistance mechanisms that are highly dependent on the environmental conditions, which in Prague, supported them in reducing the infection rates.

Differences in temperature and humidity between the two locations is the most likely explanation as these two factors are the most relevant abiotic factors (Goates, 1996). Meteorological data from BOKU (2023) shows that spring temperatures in 2022 were slightly warmer than in 2021. This could have favored pathogen activity and successful infection. Soil moisture is another relevant factor, which influences survival, teliospore germination, and seedling infection. Increased rainfall or soil moisture at sowing time in 2022 could have created better conditions for common bunt and resulted in increased disease incidence. On the other hand, if 2021 was drier or less favorable, the pathogen may have struggled to infect, resulting in lower infection rates. Furthermore, Prague and

Tulln have different soil types, organic matter content, and microbial populations. Some studies suggest that some soil microbiomes could suppress common bunt by competitive exclusion or by antifungal activities (Ritzer et al., 2021). If the soil in Prague contained larger quantities of pathogenic microorganisms or had poorer spore survival, this could have contributed to lower rates of infection.

Even though the experiments were set up to be identical, there could have been minor differences in sowing date, field history, and previous crop rotation. The plants grown in Prague could have thereby benefited from a lower field contamination. The complexity of interactions between hosts and pathogens, in regards to their environment must be considered. Susceptible genotypes in one location may perform well under different climatic or soil environments, which underlines the value of multi-location testing. Further research may also aim to identify the specific environmental or edaphic factors that result in lower common bunt infection rates and to explain natural disease suppression mechanisms.

Genotype-environment interaction may also be a reason for the difference in resistance to common bunt infection between the locations. Some genotypes may have found better growing conditions in one location or were more susceptible to poor growing conditions, resulting in faster germination or growth during the phase in which they are most vulnerable to infection. Infected plants may have prevented the formation of buntballs better, if they were less stressed under better environmental conditions. The comparison of the 2021 and 2022 experiments at the Tulln field showed a significant difference in infection rates, highlighting that environmental conditions played a significant role in disease appearance. While the same genotypes were grown in the same place, variations in the temperature of the soil, water level, and weather conditions in the two years apparently affected the severity of common bunt infections.

Furthermore, differences in the initial spore burden could have played a role. If the 2022 field contained a higher amount of residual spores in the soil from earlier infections, the disease pressure would have been greater. This is a key factor in common bunt management, as multiple infections have a tendency to accumulate in the pathogen reservoir in the soil and thereby cause more severe outbreaks in subsequent years (Wilbois et al., 2007). The differences observed, in the levels of resistance among the winter wheat genotypes used for testing, suggests that there is more than a single mechanism involved in common bunt resistance. Common bunt resistance can be divided into pre-infection resistance and post-infection resistance. Certain genotypes can reduce the number

of buntballs that are formed after they have been infected (post-infection) while others can avoid infection at all (pre-infection), for example by making the environment around teliospore germination unfavorable. Since common bunt infects seedlings basically through the coleoptile, seedling vigor and quick germination can enable plants to avoid infection by being faster than fungal growth (Goates, 1996; Matanguihan et al., 2011).

The immune response and structure of the coleoptile may also be implicated. Thicker cell walls or waxier cuticle layers may provide a physical barrier to spore penetration, thereby reducing the chance for infection (Hoffmann & Waldher, 1981). Some resistant genotypes may allow initial infection but limit the progression of the pathogen inside the plant. This could for example be achieved by hypersensitive responses in the infected tissue that trigger programmed cell death to prevent further advancement of the pathogen. Certain genes, such as those coding for antifungal proteins or lignification enzymes, may also enhance resistance to common bunt (Ritzer et al., 2021).

Despite the great differences the genotypes showed in the experiments, some genotypes were consistently resistant in both years and both locations. This demonstrates the need for multi-year testing in different locations, to identify wheat varieties with consistent resistance under changing environmental conditions. Further studies could strive to explain the specific interactions between resistance genes, environmental factors and the pathogen in order to enhance breeding practices and refine resistance screening methods. Moreover, the effectiveness of agricultural disease management practices could be improved by a better understanding of the factors that drive common bunt infection in certain genotypes.

Growing genetic resistant varieties is a valuable tool to manage common bunt in organic agriculture. Nevertheless, the addition of adjusted agronomic practices, especially crop rotation, is crucial in disease control, since the spores of common bunt can remain viable in soil for several years (Wilbois et al., 2007). Rotating wheat with non host crops, such as legumes or brassicas, reduces the spore load and infection risk. The findings of this study show that resistance alone may not be enough, particularly under high disease pressure. Therefore a combination of multiple disease management techniques is necessary to ensure stable, high quality yields.

Seed treatments can also be applied as a form of disease management. Hot water seed treatments were successful in eliminating teliospores from seeds, while biological control products like

Pseudomonas fluorescens, *Pseudomonas chlororaphis* and *Bacillus subtilis* have potential as alternative strategies for organic farming systems (Berninger, 2016, Spieß et al. 2015). Chemical seed treatment is a highly effective method of prevention against common bunt infection in conventional agriculture. Due to common bunts economic impact, the integration of seed treatment with resistant genotypes could be a second line of protection. Sowing routine alteration and field sanitation can further help to reduce infections. Effective farm machinery cleaning and utilization of not contaminated seed also limits the spread of spores. Additionally, wheat can be planted in less favorable conditions for infection by common bunt, such as optimizing time of sowing and drained soils to possibly restrict the pathogen to establish itself. The variation in infection rates amongst the genotypes in the different locations shows, how environment-genotype interaction plays a major role in disease severity. This further emphasizes the necessity for site specific as well as genotype specific management practices. The use of resistant genotypes can be a major tool in common bunt management in organic agriculture, and to some extent in conventional agriculture as well. Some genotypes in this study expressed high resistance in all conditions, making them preferred subjects for further breeding efforts, while others were more susceptible than expected. Nevertheless, even the less resistant genotypes may contribute certain resistance genes to the genetic reservoir that can be useful for future breeding efforts.

These findings demonstrate the difficulties and opportunities of breeding for common bunt resistance. While some genotypes displayed stable high resistance, others were extremely variable across locations and years. In future breeding, the focus should be to select genotypes with stable resistance across a variety of environmental conditions, to achieve a reliable form of disease control for organic winter wheat production.

6. Conclusion

Chemical dressing has been found to be the most effective method of preventing common bunt infection in wheat crops (Hoffmann 1982). Therefore, common bunt infections in conventional farming have been greatly minimized. However, in organic farming, which does not permit the use of chemical dressing, the development and use of genetically resistant wheat varieties has become the norm as a way of minimizing yield and quality losses from infection by common bunt (Ritzer et al. 2021). It is required that breeding programs target the development of genotypes resistant to common bunt in a wide range of environment conditions to maintain a small variation in the level

of resistance. Today, some of the genotypes have already been found to be fully resistant, with infections less than 0.01% (Spieß et al. 2015; Ritzer et al. 2021; Dumalasova and Grausgruber 2021), providing a great basis for further research and breeding. Apart from achieving a low overall infection level (CB.150) as a main goal, resistance breeding should further target a low level of seed infection (CBS.50) and buntballs weight (CBWT.), to provide an additional barrier once a plant is infected, since these factors greatly affect the overall yield and grain quality.

The field experiments conducted in Prague and Tulln demonstrated the extreme variability in infection rates among different winter wheat genotypes in different environmental conditions, highlighting the complexity of host-pathogen interaction and confirming, that environmental factors such as soil moisture and temperature, are indeed relevant factors for infection severity. The comparison of significant infection parameters (CB.150, CBWT, and CBS.50) provided valuable information about the degree of resistance that is expressed by different genotypes, with some genotypes expressing uniformly high resistance, while others showed unusual susceptibility or a high genotype–environment interaction. This further demonstrates the need for breeding programmes to test their genetic material in multiple locations in order to identify genotypes that have stable resistance under diverse conditions. In particular the genotypes 516_EX01.6K, 521_EX08.1G, 522_EX09.4G, 559_EX06.14, G559_EX06.4, 702-1102C, BONNEVILLE, UI SRG, BLIZZARD, and ARISTARO displayed outstanding resistance in all experiments and are therefore promising material for following breeding programs.

Future research will need to further examine the genetic determination of resistance through genomic tools and explain the molecular basis of the different forms of resistance. Additionally, the integration of MAS and genomic selection could accelerate the development of wheat lines that are more resistant to common bunt and well suited to upcoming challenges. This work aims to contribute to the body of knowledge, that is required in breeding disease resistant winter wheat varieties and provides another step towards enhancing organic agriculture, food security, and environmental sustainability.

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References

- Barbercheck, M., Kiernan, N. E., Hulting, A. G., Duiker, S., Hyde, J., Karsten, H., & Sanchez, E. (2012). Meeting the ‘multi-’ requirements in organic agriculture research: Successes, challenges and recommendations for multifunctional, multidisciplinary, participatory projects. *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 27(2), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170511000214>
- Berninger, T. (2016). *Development of formulations for plant beneficial bacterial inoculants* (Doctoral dissertation, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien). Universität für Bodenkultur Wien. Retrieved from <https://permalink.obvsg.at/bok/AC12609082>
- Börner, H., Schlüter, K., & Aumann, J. (2009). *Pflanzenkrankheiten und Pflanzenschutz* (8th ed.). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-49068-5>
- Dumalasova, V., & Grausgruber, H. (2021). Research on common bunt of wheat at the Crop Research Institute within the ECOBREED project. In 72. *Tagung der Vereinigung der Pflanzenzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs* (Nov 22–24, 2021, Raumberg-Gumpenstein). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5667799>
- Duveiller, E., Singh, R. P., & Nicol, J. M. (2007). The challenges of maintaining wheat productivity: Pests, diseases, and potential epidemics. *Euphytica*, 157(3), 417–430. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10681-007-9380-z>
- Erenstein, O., Jaleta, M., Mottaleb, K. A., Sonder, K., Donovan, J., & Braun, H.-J. (2022). Global trends in wheat production, consumption, and trade. In P. Langridge (Ed.), *Wheat improvement* (pp. 47–66). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90673-3_4
- Fair, K. R., Bauch, C. T., & Anand, M. (2017). Dynamics of the global wheat trade network and resilience to shocks. *Scientific Reports*, 7, 7177. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-07202-y>
- FiBL & IFOAM – Organics International. (2024). *The World of Organic Agriculture: Statistics and Emerging Trends 2024* (H. Willer, J. Trávníček, & B. Schlatter, Eds.). Research Institute of

Organic Agriculture (FiBL) & IFOAM – Organics International. Retrieved March 8, 2025, from https://www.fibl.org/fileadmin/documents/shop/1747-organic-world-2024_light.pdf

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2020). *World food and agriculture – Statistical yearbook 2020*. FAO. Retrieved March 8, 2025, from <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/fe3b44ad-553a-4d2f-b8d9-d0ef1dc509ed/content>

Gaudet, D. A., & Puchalski, B. J. (1995). Influence of temperature on interaction of resistance genes in spring wheat differentials with races of common bunt (*Tilletia tritici* and *T. laevis*). *Canadian Journal of Plant Science*, 75(3), 745–749. <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjps95-126>

Goates, B. J. (2012). Identification of new pathogenic races of common bunt and dwarf bunt fungi, and evaluation of known races using an expanded set of differential wheat lines. *Plant Disease*, 96(3), 361–369. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-04-11-0339>

Gomiero, T., Pimentel, D., & Paoletti, M. G. (2011). Environmental impact of different agricultural management practices: Conventional vs. organic agriculture. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 30(1–2), 95–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352689.2011.554355>

Hoffmann, J. A. (1982). Bunt of wheat. *Plant Disease*, 66, 979–986. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-66-979>

Hoffmann, J. A., & Waldher, J. T. (1981). Chemical seed treatments for controlling seedborne and soilborne common bunt of wheat. *Plant Disease*, 65(3), 256–259. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-65-256>

International Centre for Agricultural Research in Dry Areas (ICARDA), Rabat Morocco, Tadesse, W., Halila, H., Jamal, M., Hanafi, S., Assefa, S., Oweis, T., & Baum, M. (2017). Role of Sustainable Wheat Production to Ensure Food Security in the CWANA region. *Journal of Experimental Biology and Agricultural Sciences*, 15–32. [https://doi.org/10.18006/2017.5\(Spl-1-SAFSAW\).S15.S32](https://doi.org/10.18006/2017.5(Spl-1-SAFSAW).S15.S32)

LfL. (2023). *Steinbrand (Tilletia caries) und Zwergsteinbrand (Tilletia controversa)*. Bayerische

Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft, Freising. Retrieved January 27, 2023, from <https://www.lfl.bayern.de/ite/futterwirtschaft/048863/index.php>

Lowder, S. K., Sánchez, M. V., & Bertini, R. (2021). Which farms feed the world and has farmland become more concentrated? *World Development*, *142*, 105455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2021.105455>

Matanguihan, J. B., Murphy, K. M., & Jones, S. S. (2011). Control of common bunt in organic wheat. *Plant Disease*, *95*(2), 92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-09-10-0620>

Momeni, H., Akhavan, A., Aboukhaddour, R., Javan-Nikkhah, M., Razavi, M., Naghavi, M. R., & Strelkov, S. E. (2019). Simple sequence repeat marker analysis reveals grouping of *Pyrenophora tritici-repentis* isolates based on geographic origin. *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology*, *41*(2), 218–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07060661.2019.1566178>

NÖ Landes-Landwirtschaftskammer & AGES. (2011). *Brandiger Weizen: Ein massives Problem für die Vermarktbarkeit von Getreide – Steinbrand nachhaltig verhindern*. NÖ Landes-Landwirtschaftskammer & AGES, Wien. Retrieved on March 8, 2024, from https://ooe.lko.at/media.php?filename=download%3D%2F2012.11.05%2F1352121564557127.pdf&rn=Broschuere+Brandiger+Weizen_klein.pdf

Reynolds, M. P., & Braun, H.-J. (2022). Wheat improvement. In M. P. Reynolds & H.-J. Braun (Eds.), *Wheat improvement* (pp. 3–15). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90673-3_1

Ritzer, E., Ehn, M., Oberforster, M., & Buerstmayr, H. (2021). Comparison of pathogenicity of Austrian isolates of *Tilletia caries* on common wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). In *72. Tagung der Vereinigung der Pflanzenzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs* (Nov 22–24, 2021, Raumberg-Gumpenstein). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5667799>

Shewry, P. R. (2009). Wheat. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, *60*(6), 1537–1553. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erp058>

Shiferaw, B., Smale, M., Braun, H.-J., Duveiller, E., Reynolds, M., & Muricho, G. (2013). Crops

that feed the world 10. Past successes and future challenges to the role played by wheat in global food security. *Food Security*, 5(3), 291–317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-013-0263-y>

Spieß, H., Ewald, B., & Stoll, E. (2015). *Weizensteinbrand*. Institut für Biologesch Landwirtschaft an Agrarkultur Lëtzebuerg (IBLA) & Bio-Lëtzebuerg - Vereenegung fir Bio-Landwirtschaft Lëtzebuerg asbl. Retrieved March 5, 2025, from https://ibla.lu/_res/uploads/2016/07/Weizensteinbrand.pdf

Universität für Bodenkultur Wien. (2023). *Institut für Pflanzenbau, Standort Tulln (UFT), Wetterdaten 2020 – 2023*. Retrieved January 27, 2023, from <https://boku.ac.at/dnw/pb/forschung/wetterdaten/standort-tulln-uft>

Voit, B., Dressler, M., & Killermann, B. (2012). Warum sind Steinbrand und Zwergsteinbrand derzeit nicht nur im ökologischen Getreidebau ein Problem? In Vereinigung der Pflanzenzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs & Höhere Bundeslehr- und Forschungsanstalt für Landwirtschaft Raumberg-Gumpenstein (Eds.), *Tagungsband der 62. Jahrestagung der Vereinigung der Pflanzenzüchter und Saatgutkaufleute Österreichs* (pp. 73–76). Lehr- und Forschungszentrum für Landwirtschaft Raumberg-Gumpenstein, Irndning. Retrieved March 5, 2025, from http://www.saatgut-austria.at/MEDIA/2011_tagungsband_web_2.pdf

Wilbois, K.-P., Vogt-Kaute, W., Spieß, H., Jahn, M., & Koch, E. (n.d.). *Leitfaden Saatgutgesundheit im Ökologischen Landbau – Ackerkulturen*. Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau e. V. (FiBL Deutschland e. V.). Retrieved March 5, 2025, from <https://www.fibl.org/fileadmin/documents/shop/1480-saatgesundheit-ackerkulturen.pdf>

Appendix

Genotypes tested for common bunt infection in Tulln 2022

GEN	CB150%	CBWT%
474_U0635-36K	86.00	81.18
516_EX01.10G_14027	4.00	0.00
516_EX01.10G_14027	0.67	0.38
516_EX01.5K_14012	15.67	1.28
516_EX01.6K_14004	0.34	0.00
516_EX01.GN0547_14070	20.00	3.97
517_EX02.10_14072	5.96	0.54
517_EX02.11K_14016	8.00	0.14
517_EX02.KN0532A_14010	2.01	0.40
518_EX03.11G_14047	10.00	0.26
518_EX03.8G_14065	6.96	1.31
518_EX03.KN0533B	22.15	1.37
521_EX08.11K_14083	6.57	1.12
521_EX08.14K_14022	10.33	0.74
521_EX08.1G_14073	0.00	0.00
521_EX08.3K_14075	6.00	1.53
521_EX08.GN0533A	7.33	0.91
521_EX08.KN0533B	10.67	1.08
522_EX09.4G_14021	0.67	0.00
522_EX09.6GUF_14006	8.02	1.81
527_EX14.5_14054	3.97	0.94
527_EX14.GN0539A_14052	10.00	1.76
528_EX15.11GK_14069	2.00	0.02
528_EX15.GN0544	10.67	1.33
534_EX21.3_14025	5.33	1.19
534_EX21.5K_14015	10.34	0.40
534_EX21.7K_14071	24.67	2.13
559_EX06.14G_14038	0.00	0.00
559_EX06.4_14079	0.00	0.00
559_EX06.9G_14090	11.62	1.35

561_EX13.7K_14056	20.67	3.31
561_EX13.8G_14044	31.33	2.76
561_EX13.GN0540A_14011	12.67	1.45
562_EX22_U0322K	41.33	10.80
563_EX23_U0317-18K	29.03	7.16
564_EX24_U0319K	46.98	20.03
564_EX24_U0321K	47.00	26.74
565_EX25_U0320K	17.33	8.40
567_EX27_U0308G	15.28	4.30
568_EX28_U0312K	6.31	0.78
569_EX29_U0313-14G	3.69	0.46
570_EX30_U0310-11G	1.00	0.12
570_EX30_U0310-11K	2.00	0.19
571_EX31_U0309B.G	0.00	0.00
572_EX32_U0315-16G	9.00	0.99
573_U0525-26K	15.45	3.58
574_U0635-36G	74.00	48.98
575_U0637-38G	70.00	51.19
575_U0637-38K	55.70	20.43
576_U0639-41K	87.67	77.04
577_U0642G	35.33	8.03
585_U0718K	58.00	4.64
617_U0509-10K	87.33	52.20
666_EX33_U0307G	16.67	2.31
7021102C_14076	0.00	0.00
ARISTARO_14039	0.00	0.00
BUTARO_14017	81.33	36.25
DELORIS_14024	2.00	0.11
GENIUS_14031	24.00	2.54
SEC261_14043	52.05	10.15
SPONTAN_14018	45.70	9.09
SU_MENDOZA	16.33	0.75
SW_MAGNIFIK	0.00	0.00
TILLIKO_14002	43.62	9.35
UI SRG_14029	0.67	0.01
UNITAR_14051	10.00	2.36

Genotypes tested for common bunt infection in Tulln 2021

GEN	CB150%	BUNTWT%
516_EX01-10G	2.67	1.51
516_EX01-11G	5.33	1.03
516_EX01-5K	7.40	1.14
516_EX01-6K	0.00	0.00
516_EX01G-N-0547	8.00	2.47
516_EX01K-N-0547	30.67	5.76
517_EX02-10	8.67	4.22
517_EX02-11K	6.00	0.49
517_EX02G-N-0532A	28.67	4.79
517_EX02K-N-0532A	3.26	0.92
518_EX03-11G	16.00	2.19
518_EX03-3K	66.00	32.21
518_EX03-8G	1.33	0.04
518_EX03K-N-0533B	9.25	2.66
521_EX08-11K	7.33	2.01
521_EX08-14K	7.33	1.06
521_EX08-1G	0.00	0.00
521_EX08-3K	15.87	5.59
521_EX08G-N-0533A	5.61	1.52
521_EX08K-N-0533B	18.67	4.58
522_EX09-4G	0.67	0.00
522_EX09-6GUF	11.33	1.02
522_EX09G-N-0543	36.20	9.63
522_EX09K-N-0543	24.67	10.32
527_EX14-12	20.67	6.49
527_EX14-5	10.00	5.15
527_EX14G-N-0539A	12.00	2.19
527_EX14K-N-0539B	26.67	8.39
528_EX15-11GK	13.23	0.91
528_EX15-4G	30.67	13.75
528_EX15G-N-0544	17.33	1.93
534_EX21-3	12.00	3.27
534_EX21-5K	2.01	0.39

534_EX21-7K	16.00	2.71
534_EX21K-N-0548B	55.33	17.58
559_EX06-14G	0.67	0.00
559_EX06-4	0.00	0.00
559_EX06-9G	6.00	1.77
561_EX13-7K	33.19	3.57
561_EX13-8G	15.33	2.98
561_EX13G-N-0540A	13.33	2.59
561_EX13K-N-0540A	40.67	11.06
7021102C	2.00	0.00
ALESSIO	57.33	47.22
ANNIE	81.33	56.59
ARISTARO	0.00	0.00
BRANDEX	58.00	22.45
BUTARO	25.00	4.18
CREATOR	22.00	5.83
DELORIS	1.00	0.00
EHOGOLD	68.67	40.00
GENIUS	16.00	2.13
GLOSA	31.17	5.55
GRAZIARO	61.34	36.66
HEERUP	21.33	8.52
IS LAUDIS	20.00	7.60
Mv KAREJ	42.67	11.19
Mv KOLOMPOS	69.33	41.09
PIZZA	38.67	15.00
PS DOBROMILA	32.67	12.23
PURINO	71.33	35.11
RED RUSSIAN	49.33	29.29
ROYAL	50.67	30.47
SEC-261-05	10.00	1.03
SEC-290-08-1a (RUEBEZAHL)	45.00	21.41
SEC-313-10-1a (BLICKFANG)	74.06	49.50
SHERIFF	58.00	57.62
SKAGIT 1109	60.00	33.84
SKAGIT 1209	46.23	13.12

SPONTAN	17.47	3.14
TENGRI	63.33	34.09
TILLEXUS	55.33	48.42
TILLIKO	24.00	13.61
TILLSTOP	52.00	41.11
TOBIAS	64.00	16.56
UI-SRG	0.00	0.00
UNITAR	6.00	0.00
URSITA	36.67	4.54
VIKI	38.98	22.11
WENDELIN	41.33	29.74
WITAL	62.00	27.14
WIWA	77.93	74.68

Genotypes tested for common bunt infection in Prague

GEN	CB%PRAGUE
516_EX01.10G_14027	5.3
516_EX01.11G_14048	0.0
516_EX01.5K_14012	1.7
516_EX01.6K_14004	0.0
516_EX01.GN0547_14070	3.6
517_EX02.11K_14016	2.2
517_EX02.KN0532A_14010	1.3
517_EX02.KN0532A_14010	4.5
518_EX03.8G_14065	0.0
518_EX03.KN0533B	1.5
521_EX08.11K_14083	0.9
521_EX08.14K_14022	0.0
521_EX08.1G_14073	0.0
521_EX08.3K_14075	6.1
521_EX08.GN0533A	6.2
521_EX08.KN0533B	2.3
522_EX09.4G_14021	0.0
522_EX09.6GUF_14006	0.0

528_EX15.11GK_14069	6.8
534_EX21.5K_14015	2.3
559_EX06.14G_14038	0.5
559_EX06.4_14079	0.0
559_EX06.9G_14090	1.1
561_EX13.7K_14056	0.0
565_EX25_U0320K	0.0
567_EX27_U0308G	0.0
568_EX28_U0312K	0.0
569_EX29_U0313-14G	2.2
570_EX30_U0310-11G	0.0
572_EX32_U0315-16G	3.7
7021102C_14076	0.0
ARISTARO_14039	0.0
BUTARO_14017	3.5
DELORIS_14024	0.0
GENIUS_14031	0.9
SEC261_14043	8.2
SPONTAN_14018	2.1
TILLIKO_14002	0.0
UI SRG_14029	0.0
UNITAR_14051	0.0